

Slicer FSP: An Open-Source Modular Platform for Reproducible Dental Implant Surgery Planning

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Abstract

Purpose To develop an open-source application composed of specialized modules for oral and dental implant surgery planning, built on the medical imaging platform 3D Slicer. The goal was to integrate a fragmented set of tools into a unified, reproducible, and computationally coherent workflow.

Methods Six Python scripted custom modules were developed and combined with three built-in modules and five 3D Slicer extensions to form the Slicer–Free Surgical Planner (Slicer FSP). The system implements a complete digital workflow, from CBCT import and preprocessing to prosthetic simulation, implant planning, and surgical guide design. The architecture emphasizes modularity, interoperability, automated data handling, and standardized coordinate export to support downstream computational tasks.

Results Compared with using multiple independent 3D Slicer modules, Slicer FSP significantly reduced workflow complexity and overall working time. The integrated design introduced new technical capabilities, including automated slice and implant coordinate export, enhanced alignment tools, top-down implant simulation, improved data management, and a bilingual interface. These features increased reproducibility, reduced user-dependent variability, and enabled consistent execution of complex planning steps.

Conclusion Slicer FSP is an open, extensible, and transparent platform for oral surgery and implant planning, offering a technically robust alternative to commercial systems. Its open-source availability supports further development, validation, and integration into research pipelines, facilitating broader adoption of reproducible, modular, and community-driven digital workflows.

Introduction

Static computer-assisted implant surgery (sCAIS) has been shown to provide significantly higher accuracy compared with conventional freehand implant placement techniques[1–6]. As a result, digital planning and surgical guides have become widely integrated into clinical practice.

A large number of proprietary commercial software packages are available for implant planning and surgical guide fabrication. However, their use is associated with limitations such as high cost, lack of code transparency, and restricted ability to customize or extend functionality. Although free and open-source software (FOSS) could serve as a viable alternative, the relevant literature in dentistry remains limited and fragmented[7–15].

3D Slicer is a free and open-source platform for visualization, processing, and analysis of medical and biomedical data, as well as for image-guided intervention planning[16]. A previous study investigated the use of 3D Slicer for implant planning and accuracy assessment. Although the results were consistent with the international literature, the required workflow was complex, time-consuming, and dependent on multiple modules[17].

The present study represents the first systematic customization of 3D Slicer for oral surgery planning, aiming to create an integrated, simplified, and extensible application for dental implant planning.

Materials and Methods

Slicer–Free Surgical Planner (Slicer FSP) was developed on the open-source platform 3D Slicer (version 5.10.0), following the official build guidelines. The development environment included Visual Studio Community 2022, Visual Studio Build Tools 2019, Qt 5.15.2, CMake 3.26.4, and NSIS 3.11. After cloning the 3D Slicer source code from GitHub, the custom modules were integrated into the application, and interface-level modifications were applied without altering core logic components. This ensured compatibility with the existing Slicer API and preserved full reproducibility.

Slicer FSP was designed as a modular computational workflow combining six Python-scripted custom modules, three built-in modules (Markups, Segment Editor, Dynamic Modeler), five extensions (Dental Segmentator[10, 18], SlicerIGT[19], SlicerMorph[20–21], SegmentEditorExtraEffects, SurfaceWrapSolidify[22]), and additional logic components such as Segment Statistics and SubjectHierarchyTreeView. All custom modules were implemented in Python 3.9 and adhere to the 3D Slicer 5.10.0 API. A unified top-level navigation menu and bilingual interface were added to standardize user interaction and reduce workflow fragmentation. The overall architecture forms a coherent pipeline that begins with CBCT preprocessing and ends with surgical guide design (Fig. 1).

Module Overview

1. Oral Surgery Module Home

Central navigation hub providing structured access to all Slicer FSP modules and predefined layouts.

2. Dental Implant Imaging

CBCT preprocessing module supporting:

- DICOM metadata extraction
- Automated conversion of Dental Segmentator outputs to 3D models
- Cross-section curve creation with adjustable point density(Fig. 2)
- Slice-driven navigation with tilt control and coordinate export
- Multi-slice dynamic layouts with export to PNG/PDF(Fig. 3)
- Segment statistics via integrated logic components(Fig. 3)

3. Registration Module (Fig. 4)

Implements two alignment strategies:

Point-based registration

- Import scan-derived model
- Select ≥ 4 corresponding points
- Compute rigid transformation until $RMSE \leq 0.2$ mm

FastModelAlign (SlicerMorph)

- Rigid alignment without scaling
- Validation via point cloud subsampling

Post-processing includes ACVD mesh repair, undercut detection, and generation of the GuideBase model (Fig. 5).

4. Virtual Prosthetics

Provides prosthetic simulation with:

- Virtual tooth import and positioning(Fig. 6)
- Transformation export/import(Fig. 7)
- Full model management via SubjectHierarchyTreeView

5. Generic Implant Creator

Implements implant creation and placement with:

- Parametric pre-implant generation(Fig. 8)
- Dynamic orientation via platform–apex points
- Automated implant selection by jaw/brand/system(Fig. 9)
- Coordinate export/import for reproducible planning
- Full implant and ring management via SubjectHierarchyTreeView

6. Oral Surgery Data

Centralized data management module organizing:

- Implants
- Models, points, curves
- Segments

All properties are editable to support structured workflows.

A summary of module capabilities is provided in Table 1.

Surgical Guide Design Workflow(Fig. 10)

Guide fabrication is performed using Dynamic Modeler and Segment Editor tools:

1. Closed Curve definition on GuideBase
2. CurveCut extraction and Hollow operation (3 mm shell)
3. Surface refinement (Closing, Logical Operators, Scissors, Median smoothing)
4. Export to STL/OBJ

Results

Slicer-FSP was successfully developed. Its structure and workflow enable faster and simpler procedures within the complex 3D Slicer environment. New functionalities include:

- Export of slice and implant coordinates
- Top-down implant planning
- Unified multi-slice layout
- Multiple alignment methods
- Automated segmentation
- Free export of generated models in various formats
- Expandable prosthetic and implant lists
- Bilingual interface
- Enhanced data visualization and management

Implant planning time per jaw ranged from 30–90 minutes, depending on case complexity. Processing time depends on hardware; on the development laptop (i7-12700H 2.3 GHz, 32 GB RAM, NVIDIA RTX A1000 4 GB), automatic segmentation required less than 10 minutes.

The application is freely available at '<https://freesurgplan.edu.gr/>' with three download options: (1) executable (Slicer FSP), (2) Python-scripted custom modules, (3) build source code.

The website also provides step-by-step tutorial videos covering the entire workflow. The first release currently supports Windows; macOS and Linux support will follow.

Discussion

Commercial dental software has accelerated the adoption of digital technologies in implantology. However, high cost, closed-source architecture, and limited customizability restrict accessibility and reduce the clinical feedback essential for advancing digital methods. This study demonstrates the

feasibility of developing a specialized implant-planning environment entirely within 3D Slicer, leveraging its modular architecture and extensible API.

Slicer FSP consolidates multiple independent modules, extensions, and manual steps into a unified computational pipeline. This integration reduces workflow fragmentation, minimizes user-dependent variability, and enables consistent execution of complex planning tasks. The six custom modules interact directly with built-in logic components and external extensions, forming a coherent data flow from CBCT preprocessing to surgical guide design.

Exporting DICOM metadata, slice coordinates, and platform–apex coordinates provides structured datasets suitable for downstream computational research, including machine-learning models for automated implant-position prediction[23]. Prosthetic simulation preceding implant insertion ensures top-down planning[24]. Unlike commercial systems that determine the optimal slice after implant adjustment (implant-driven), Slicer FSP selects the optimal slice orientation first (slice-driven), offering more comprehensive 3D control. A key advantage of 3D Slicer is the ability to import multiple CBCT scans, enabling comparative measurements such as postoperative assessments.

Strengths

Slicer FSP consolidates previously fragmented steps into a unified computational workflow, reducing complexity and enabling consistent execution of implant-planning tasks. Its open-source architecture ensures full transparency, reproducibility, and independent verification, while interoperability with built-in 3D Slicer logic components and widely used extensions enhances flexibility. Automated coordinate export provides structured geometric data suitable for downstream computational research, including machine-learning applications. The modular design supports extensibility, allowing users to expand prosthetic and implant libraries and adapt the system to diverse research or educational needs. Top-down planning, slice-driven navigation, and predefined layouts help reduce user-dependent variability.

Limitations

As with 3D Slicer, Slicer FSP is intended for research and educational use rather than clinical deployment. Users unfamiliar with medical-imaging software may initially encounter a learning curve, although guided layouts mitigate this. Performance is hardware-dependent, particularly for segmentation and rendering tasks. The current release supports Windows only, with macOS and Linux versions planned. Some functionalities rely on external extensions that may evolve independently. Finally, although the system supports coordinate export and model comparison, quantitative accuracy-validation tools are not embedded directly into the workflow and require external analysis.

Future Work

Future development of Slicer FSP will focus on expanding its computational capabilities and improving interoperability within the 3D Slicer ecosystem. Integration of quantitative accuracy-assessment tools, including automated deviation analysis and implant–bone proximity metrics, would enable direct validation of planning outcomes within the platform. Additional work will explore the incorporation of machine-learning models for automated implant-position prediction, leveraging the standardized coordinate exports already implemented in the system.

Cross-platform support for macOS and Linux is planned to broaden accessibility and facilitate adoption in diverse research environments. Enhancing real-time rendering performance and optimizing segmentation workflows for lower-performance hardware will further improve usability. Finally, future versions may incorporate customizable surgical-guide templates, parametric guide-tube generation, and automated quality-control checks to support more advanced and fully integrated digital workflows.

Conclusion

Slicer FSP represents a structured and extensible open-source platform for oral and dental implant surgery planning, built as an integrated suite of modules within the 3D Slicer ecosystem. Rather than functioning as a standalone application, it operates as a coordinated computational workflow that leverages and extends existing Slicer capabilities. The system streamlines CBCT processing, prosthetic simulation, implant planning, and surgical-guide design while introducing new tools for alignment, coordinate export, and data management.

Although primarily intended for research and educational use, Slicer FSP provides a technically robust alternative to commercial solutions and supports reproducible, transparent, and community-driven development. Its open availability enables further refinement, validation, and integration into advanced computational pipelines, including AI-assisted planning and automated surgical workflows.

Declarations

Code Availability

To ensure full transparency and reproducibility, the complete Slicer-FSP project—including the source code, custom modules, modified 3D Slicer files, and the packaged executable—is openly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/dnt102/Slicer-FSP>) and permanently archived on Zenodo under a concept DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18596636>), which always points to the latest version.

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Table 1

Table 1 is available in the Supplementary Files.

Figures

Slicer-FSP

Figure 1

Workflow diagram of the Slicer-FSP and the connections between scripted modules, built-in modules, and extensions. The central module links, data links, and overall workflow direction are illustrated.

Figure 2

Curve point-density adjustment. **a** Resample distance 3 mm (102 points). **b** Resample distance 0.3 mm (337 points).

Figure 3

Dynamic multi-slice layout displaying one slice per selected curve position during slice-driven navigation. Inset: clinical image after removal of the cystic lesion.

Figure 4

Alignment options. **a** Point-based registration with deviation control. **b** Point-cloud model matching. **a↔b** Comparison of the results of the two methods.

Figure 5

a Aligned scan-derived model. **b** Post-processing of the aligned model. **c** Undercut detection (red). **d** Undercut exclusion (green). **e** Final model (GuideBase) for surgical guide design.

Figure 6

Selection of prosthetic components from a customizable list and simulation at potential implant slice-positions.

Figure 7

Implant site determination based on slice-driven navigation and prosthetic simulation, with dynamic visualization of the selected positions.

Figure 8

Creation and evaluation of pre-implants at the selected positions, with appropriate dimensions and orientation.

Figure 9

Selection of an implant from a customizable list and alignment with the pre-implant. The example shows an MIS-7 implant, but any implant system can be added.

Figure 10

Surgical guide design workflow. **a** Closed curve definition on GuideBase. **b** CurveCut extraction. **c** Hollow operation (3 mm shell). **d** Shell refinement and boolean ring integration. **e** Final smoothing. **f** Export to STL/OBJ.

Supplementary Files

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- [Table.doc](#)